

Developing a Draft Primary Mathematics Curriculum: A Vision for Equitable, Accessible and Inclusive Learning Experiences for Every Child

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The National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA) advises the Minister for Education on curriculum and assessment for early childhood education, primary and post-primary schools. Inclusion and the promotion of equitable access, engagement and challenge are core considerations for NCCA's development of curriculum and assessment in Ireland. At primary level, a draft mathematics curriculum is in development and this paper provides an inside glance into the curriculum development process with a spotlight on inclusion. It is situated in broader policy and research contexts and describes the incorporation of stakeholder voice and agency in shaping and refining developments. The paper also references some key ideas and considerations which guide the curriculum development process in service of more equitable, accessible and inclusive mathematical learning experiences for every child.

Introduction

The National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA) advises the Minister for Education on curriculum and assessment for early childhood education, primary and post-primary schools. As part of Primary Curriculum review and redevelopment, a draft Primary Mathematics Curriculum (PMC) is currently in development. Central to this curriculum is a vision for equitable, accessible and inclusive learning experiences for every child. This paper begins by describing key contexts for the curriculum development process. Following this, some aspects of the research which underpinned this vision for inclusion and equity in the curriculum are presented. The paper then shows how inclusion and equity have been incorporated into the process through stakeholder voice and agency. In the latter part of this paper, some of the key ideas and considerations that inform the development of the draft PMC are discussed and summarised, and their application to the design and development process is described.

A Fresh Vision for Children's Mathematical Learning

In the proposed draft PMC, mathematics is characterised as the study of the relationships, connections and patterns that surround us, which in turn allows us to understand and engage fully with our world. Every child, without exception, is considered to have an innate, intuitive and instinctive sense of mathematics; is capable of using these tools and engaging with mathematical concepts and ideas from birth; and can deepen and develop her/his learning over time. The overarching aim of the proposed draft PMC is for every child to develop mathematical proficiency, namely: conceptual understanding, procedural fluency, adaptive reasoning, strategic competence and productive disposition. As children engage with increasingly sophisticated mathematical learning experiences their mathematical proficiency is developed and refined.

The draft PMC prioritises and promotes equity and access for all children, irrespective of their cognitive ability, cultural context, or socio-economic background. Indeed, the development of the draft PMC is situated in the revision and redevelopment of the broader primary curriculum, where inclusion, access and equity are central to the vision for children's learning in primary school (NCCA, 2020). The Draft Primary Curriculum Framework strongly recognises the agency and professionalism of teachers in managing the complexity of learning in the classroom and the diversity of children's learning journeys. It holds that inclusion, access and equity for children in the classroom is realised when teachers engage children in appropriately playful and engaging learning experiences which are tailored to their individual needs, strengths and interests.

Context for Developments

Policy Context

In broad policy terms, inclusion is described as a process of addressing and responding to the diverse needs of learners, whilst simultaneously removing barriers so that each child can gain the maximum benefit from his or her school experience (National Council for Special Education [NCSE], 2011). In the last decade, a number of developments have occurred that are relevant to curriculum development. For example, the increased numbers of children entering primary schools has led to increased provision for children with special educational needs (SEN) (NCSE, 2019) and the Irish Government's ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in March 2018 has prompted policy change. Further, the new model of special education teaching allocation (Department of Education and Skills [DES], 2017) aims to support and promote a whole-school approach to SEN provision, as well as a commitment to the inclusion of pupils with SEN in mainstream schools. However, it also recognises that in some instances, a minority of pupils with significant and enduring needs require more specialist settings such as special school placements or special classes in mainstream schools.

The characterisation of an inclusive school culture set out in the most recent guidelines for primary schools (DES, 2017a) as well as other policies such as the Inclusive Framework for Schools (NCSE, 2011) and the DEIS (Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools) Action Plan (DES, 2017b) provides an important context for curriculum that serves the needs of all children in all school settings. Ambitions for promoting active participation and engagement, belonging and community, as well as high aspirations for all children's learning contribute to the development of curriculum policy in support of this vision.

Research Base

It was initially planned that the PMC would be published in two parts, the first publication being the specification for junior infants to second class, followed by the specification for third to sixth class. Subsequently, it was decided by the then Minister of Education, Richard Bruton, that the new curriculum should be published as a single specification. As a consequence of the initial plan, the research base for curriculum developments was collected in two phases. In the first phase, a systematic review of the

literature was conducted, concentrating on teaching and learning for children aged three to eight years. This comprised an international audit of mathematics curriculum policy (Burke, 2014); Research Report 17 (Dunphy et al., 2014) which focused on definitions, theories, development and progression in primary mathematics; and Research Report 18 (Dooley et al., 2014) which looked at pedagogy and learning more specifically. Drawing on this research base, a background paper and brief for development of the draft PMC (NCCA, 2016) was produced. Following the publication of the first draft specification of the PMC for junior infants to second class (NCCA, 2017), consultation took place between October 2017 to March 2018. The report from this consultation (NCCA, 2018) added significantly to the research base.

The second phase of research reports served to complement the existing research base by focusing on the senior classes of primary school. A research addendum to Research Reports 17 and 18 was compiled (Dooley, 2019) which looked at broad teaching and learning considerations for children in the upper years of primary school. This was further supplemented with five short research papers which examined core mathematical concepts, skills and processes with which children engage across the five mathematical domains (Delaney, 2020; Leavy, 2020; Nic Mhuiri, 2020a, 2020b; Twohill, 2020).

Throughout this research, myriad references are made to the importance of promoting inclusion and addressing diversity. For example, in Research Report 17 (Dunphy et al., 2014), the authors point to high-quality learning experiences that are critical to closing existing equity gaps and ensuring that every child can realise their mathematical potential. In providing such experiences, the report suggested that rather than needing distinctive teaching approaches or even distinctive curricula, what is required is a focus on addressing individual and specific needs of children. In Research Report 18 (Dooley et al, 2014), it is stressed that while learning paths are useful to illustrate a general developmental continuum of children's learning, individual children actually progress their learning in diverse and non-linear ways. Indeed, appropriately sequencing learning according to children's individual developmental paths is highlighted as a feature of 'good pedagogy'. In the research addendum to these reports (Dooley, 2019), it is again acknowledged that children have diverse ways of making sense of mathematics. Moreover, considerable attention is also paid in this report to offering an equitable curriculum through the provision of a culturally sensitive pedagogy. To do so, Sleeter's (2012, p.571) advice to educators is highlighted, "[w]hat makes more sense is for teachers to bring to the classroom an awareness of diverse cultural possibilities that might relate to their students, but then to get to know the students themselves".

Accordingly, the background paper and brief for PMC developments (NCCA, 2016) articulates a clear commitment to design an inclusive PMC for every child that promotes the principles of inclusion, equity and access. It states:

The curriculum will be developed in line with the principles of universal design for learning and as such, promote the principles of equity and access for children with a diverse range of abilities. For children with special educational needs and in particular, those with severe and profound and low moderate

needs, the curriculum will outline what is appropriate and relevant for them to know and provide differentiated support so they can access this learning. The curriculum will support children who attend Irish- and English-medium schools, and acknowledge and support children from different language backgrounds where neither English nor Irish is their first language. It will be considerate of the wide range of diverse backgrounds that children come from and their differing starting points as they enter primary school, including children from socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds. (p.57).

Voice for Inclusion and Equity

To provide a strong, representative, and responsive basis for its curriculum and development work, NCCA has established Development Groups to undertake specific tasks in curriculum areas or subjects. The Early Childhood and Primary Mathematics Development Group includes stakeholder representatives who advocate for inclusive curriculum. In consultation with the Development Group, NCCA has worked with a number of ‘critical friends’ groups with specific expertise on inclusion to gather feedback during the drafting process.

Consultation is a critical opportunity to gather feedback from children, teachers, school leaders, parents and the wider public on curriculum developments. In the context of the PMC, a draft specification for junior infants to second class was published for consultation in October 2017. As the consultation report (NCCA, 2018) noted, NCCA took a number of steps to gather feedback on how well the draft PMC addressed the issue of inclusion. For example, a diverse range of school settings was included in the school network strand of the consultation. Consultation findings show that the draft specification was recognised by schools as being very inclusive, with a number of participants acknowledging efforts made to include every child. In particular, teachers working in SEN settings welcomed the outcomes-based approach of the draft curriculum. In time, a draft of the full specification will again be published for consultation and this will provide a further opportunity for NCCA to listen and learn and subsequently improve and refine the draft in terms of equity and inclusion.

Key Considerations for Developments

The challenge of supporting and meeting the needs of all children is well recognised. In the years since the 1999 primary curriculum was introduced, there have been a number of research-based frameworks that have been devised in response to this challenge. One such prominent framework is Universal Design for Learning (UDL) (CAST, 2018). Derived from the principles of universal design in architecture, UDL is built upon the premise that designing a building or indeed a curriculum with the needs of diverse users in mind from the outset has positive outcomes for all users. In the past two decades, cultural responsiveness has also gained increasing attention and prominence in scholarly work and policy outputs. Like UDL, it is an approach to reach and include learners who may traditionally have been more marginalised. In the context of curriculum development and enactment, culturally responsive practices are important in ensuring that children’s cultural identity and references are recognised and honoured in all aspects of teaching and learning. Growing scholarly work (e.g.

Hammond, 2015; Ladson-Billings, 2011; Richards et al., 2007; Rose and Meyer, 2002) offers important considerations for developing an inclusive and equitable PMC. These include:

- Every child is capable of learning mathematics.
- Every child should have equitable access to rich, meaningful and challenging learning opportunities.
- The teacher / child relationship is central to the learning experience.
- Learning goals and outcomes should be clear and accessible, and offer an appropriate level of support, challenge and interest to every child.
- Providing children with the opportunity to engage, present and express their learning in multiple ways enriches the learning experience of every child.
- Methods and approaches should be flexible and diverse enough to provide appropriate learning experiences, challenges, and supports for every child.
- Assessment should help children to see their progress, to identify challenges and areas for support and to plan their next steps, as well as serving to help teachers adjust instruction and maximise learning.
- Inclusive and culturally inviting classrooms provide the optimal learning space where every child can appreciate his/her sameness and difference and feel like they belong.

These key considerations offer the potential to provide increased equity of access and opportunity for all children, and in doing so, presents an opportunity to address the challenges faced in meeting the needs of an increasingly diverse Irish school population.

Design and Development Process

Following the publication of the primary school mathematics curriculum in 1999, a suite of guidelines was produced by NCCA with a focus on supporting children with SEN, including guidelines for teachers of students with mild general learning disabilities, moderate general learning disabilities, and severe and profound learning difficulties. The vision for the draft PMC is that the curriculum will attend to the learning experiences for every child, notwithstanding the setting that the child might attend. Accordingly, as stated in the background paper and brief (NCCA, 2016, p.20):

The development of the new primary mathematics curriculum will be cognisant of the myriad factors impacting schools in Ireland currently, as well as new theoretical perspectives offered in the literature.

Naturally, specific supports should and will be developed to accompany the curriculum so that the individual needs of children can be supported. Like the Primary Language Curriculum / Curaclam Teanga na Bunscoile (NCCA, 2019), the draft PMC will have a Teacher Toolkit. Sample support materials, including those that highlight, support and promote opportunities for inclusive learning, are being created as part of the curriculum development process. It is intended that in the next phase of consultation, these support

materials will be reviewed and trialled in a variety of school contexts. Finally, in order to support teachers and school leaders in creating inclusive learning experiences, NCCA continues to collaborate with our partners in the Professional Development Service for Teachers (PDST) and the NCSE. Together, we are committed to ensuring that policy aspirations for inclusion and equity translate to the lived experiences of children in our schools.

Conclusion

Curriculum development in Ireland is a comprehensive process that aspires to the highest standards of rigour and integrity. Research, deliberation, consultation and networks underpin the work of the NCCA and serve to ensure that curriculum policy is inclusive of all voices. As strongly evidenced in the Draft Primary Curriculum Framework (NCCA, 2020) equitable, accessible and inclusive learning experiences are central to the vision for children's learning experiences, not least in terms of their learning in primary mathematics. Realising a vision for equity, accessibility and inclusion for every child is a challenge which requires commitment and collaboration from all stakeholders. As primary curriculum review and redevelopment continues to progress in Ireland, there is much cause for optimism that policy aspirations for greater inclusion will be realised in the lived experiences of every child.

References

- Burke, D. (2014). *Audit of mathematics curriculum policy across 12 jurisdictions: Commissioned report for National Council for Curriculum and Assessment*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. <https://ncca.ie/media/2031/audit-mathematics-curriculum-policy.pdf>
- CAST. (2018). *Universal design for learning guidelines, version 2.2*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. <http://udlguidelines.cast.org>
- Delaney, S. (2020). *Number in the senior primary classes: Commissioned research paper for National Council for Curriculum and Assessment*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. https://ncca.ie/media/4622/primary_maths_research_number_seniorclasses.pdf
- Department of Education and Skills, DES. (2017a). *Circular 0013/2017. Special education teaching allocation in mainstream primary schools*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. https://www.education.ie/en/Circulars-and-Forms/Active-Circulars/cl0013_2017.pdf
- Department of Education and Skills, DES. (2017b). *DEIS Plan 2017: Delivering equality of opportunity in schools*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. <https://www.education.ie/en/Publications/Policy-Reports/DEIS-Plan-2017.pdf>
- Dooley, T. (2019). *Learning and teaching primary mathematics: An addendum to NCCA research reports 17 and 18*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. https://ncca.ie/media/4087/primary_maths_research_addendum_2019.pdf
- Dooley, T., Dunphy, E., & Shiel, G. (2014). *Mathematics in early childhood and primary education. Research report 18: Commissioned report for National Council for*

- Curriculum and Assessment*. Retrieved June 23, 2021.
https://ncca.ie/media/2147/ncca_research_report_18.pdf
- Dunphy, E. Dooley, T., & Shiel, G. (2014). *Mathematics in early childhood and primary education. Research report 17: Commissioned report for National Council for Curriculum and Assessment*. Retrieved June 23, 2021.
https://ncca.ie/media/1494/maths_in_ecp_education_theories_progression_researchreport_17.pdf
- Hammond, Z. (2015). *Culturally responsive teaching and the brain: Promoting authentic engagement and rigor among culturally and linguistically diverse students*. Corwin.
- Ladson-Billings, G. (2011). Is meeting the diverse needs of all students possible? *Kappa Delta Pi Record*, 47, 13-15.
- Leavy, A. (2020). *Data and Chance in the senior primary classes: Commissioned research paper for National Council for Curriculum and Assessment*. Retrieved June 23, 2021.
https://ncca.ie/media/4620/primary_maths_research_data_and_chance_seniorclasses.pdf
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, NCCA. (2016). *Background paper and brief for development of a new primary mathematics curriculum*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. https://ncca.ie/media/1341/maths_background_paper_131016_tc.pdf
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, NCCA. (2017). *Primary mathematics curriculum, draft specification Junior infants to second class: For consultation*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. https://ncca.ie/media/3148/primary_mathsspec_en.pdf
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, NCCA. (2018). *Consultation report on the primary mathematics curriculum for junior infants to second class*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. https://ncca.ie/media/3605/pmc_consultation_report_july2018.pdf
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, NCCA. (2020). *Draft primary curriculum framework: For consultation*. Retrieved June 23, 2021.
<https://ncca.ie/media/4456/ncca-primary-curriculum-framework-2020.pdf>
- National Council for Special Education, NCSE. (2011). *Inclusive education framework: A guide for schools on the inclusion of pupils with special educational needs*. Retrieved June 23, 2021.
https://ncse.ie/wpcontent/uploads/2014/10/InclusiveEducationFramework_InteractiveVersion.pdf
- National Council for Special Education, NCSE. (2019). *Policy advice on special schools and classes: An inclusive education for an inclusive society?* Retrieved June 23, 2021.
https://ncse.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Progress-Report-Policy-Advice-on-Special-Schools-Classes-website-upload.pdf?fbclid=IwAR2Bbn2jdqhH0fHcexBD6HZP5eEPd9cxDRD05k5Nx5etFo3sC_YSSKdeR8U

- Nic Mhuirí, S. (2020a). *Measures in the senior primary classes: Commissioned research paper for National Council for Curriculum and Assessment*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. https://ncca.ie/media/4626/primary_maths_research_measures_seniorclasses.pdf
- Nic Mhuirí, S. (2020b). *Shape and space in the senior primary classes: Commissioned research paper for National Council for Curriculum and Assessment*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. https://ncca.ie/media/4624/primary_maths_research_shape_and_space_seniorclasses.pdf
- Richards, H., Brown, A., & Forde, T. (2007). Addressing diversity in schools: Culturally responsive pedagogy. *Teaching Exceptional Children*, 39(3), 64-68.
- Rose, D. & Meyer, A. (2002). *Teaching every student in the digital age: Universal design for learning*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Sleeter, C. (2012). Confronting the marginalization of culturally responsive pedagogy. *Urban Education*, 47(3), 562-584.
- Twohill, A. (2020). *Algebra in the senior primary classes: Commissioned research paper for National Council for Curriculum and Assessment*. Retrieved June 23, 2021. https://ncca.ie/media/4619/primary_maths_research_algebra_seniorclasses.pdf